

Synthesis of 2'-Hydroxy-5'-propionamino-4-nitro- α -methyl Chalkone

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The synthesis of α -alkylchalkones from ω -alkylacetophenones, such as, propiophenones and butyrophenones, does not seem to have been much investigated. A synthesis of benzylidenepropiophenone has been reported in literature (Abell, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1901, 79, 929) from propiophenone and benzaldehyde using alkaline condensing agents like sodium methoxide, sodium ethoxide, potassium hydroxide as well as an acid condensing agent like dry hydrogen chloride.

In the present case an attempt has been made to condense 2-hydroxy-5-propionaminopropiophenone, obtained by the Fries rearrangement of *p*-aminophenol dipropionate, with several aromatic aldehydes employing different concentrations of caustic potash solution. The condensation has been found to be successful only with *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde. The reaction seems to be more vigorous since it yields the chalkone in an hour. The reaction has been investigated using different concentrations of alkali and changing the reaction period. The reaction seems to be the most favourable with 20% KOH at room temperature for 1 hour. Phosphorus oxychloride has also been employed successfully as a condensing agent.

The chalkone has been converted into 7-propionamino-3-methyl-4'-nitroflavone by the action of selenium dioxide in amyl alcohol.

2-Hydroxy-5-propionaminopropiophenone.—The dipropionate of *p*-aminophenol, prepared from *p*-aminophenol, propionic anhydride, and pyridine, was crystallised from ethanol, m. p. 165°. (Found: N, 6.08. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_3\text{N}$ requires N, 6.33%).

p-Aminophenol dipropionate (3.0 g., 1 mol.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (6.0 g., 3.3 mols.) were heated in an oil-bath at 140° for an hour. The pale green solid, obtained on working up as usual, crystallised from dilute ethanol as pale green needles, m. p. 125° (1.8 g.). (Found: N, 6.10. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_3$ requires N, 6.33%).

2'-Hydroxy-5'-propionamino-4-nitro- α -methylchalcone.—To a hot solution of 2-hydroxy-5-propionaminopropiophenone (1.0 g., 1 mol.) and *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde (0.7 g., 1 mol.) in ethanol (20.0 c.c.) was added potassium hydroxide solution (20.0%; 20.0 c.c.)

gradually with stirring, when the colour of the reaction mixture changed from pale brown to deep red. It was then left at room temperature for 1 hour. On dilution and acidification in cold (with 5.0 c. c. of conc. HCl), an orange solid separated, which was collected, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, and crystallised from ethanol, in red brown needles, m. p. 140° (0.5 g.). (Found: C, 64.10; H, 4.69. $C_{19}H_{18}O_5N_2$ requires C, 64.40 H, 5.08%).

The *benzoyloxy derivative* crystallised from ethanol, in light brown needles, m. p. 151-52°. (Found: C, 67.79; H, 4.48. $C_{26}H_{22}N_2O_6$ requires C, 68.13; H, 4.80%).

6-Propionamino-3-methyl-4'-nitroflavone.—A mixture of the above α -methylchalcone (0.5 g.), selenium dioxide (0.5 g.), and isoamyl alcohol (15.0 c. c.) was refluxed on an oil-bath at 140-45° for 12 hours. The reaction mixture was filtered hot in order to remove the precipitated selenium and the filtrate was steam-distilled to remove isoamyl alcohol, when an orange-brown solid separated, which was washed with dilute alkali (5.0%) and crystallised from ethanol in light brown needles, m. p. 180° (0.15 g.). (Found: C, 64.42; H, 4.22. $C_{19}H_{16}N_2O_5$ requires C, 64.77; H, 4.54%).

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